

EVALUATION OF GFRP STRENGTH UNDER WATER ENVIRONMENT CONSIDERING INTERFACIAL STRENGTH DEGRADATION

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ABSTRACT

As strength degradation of GFRP occurs due to the SCC in its constituents, present paper proposes the prediction method of the residual strength considering the microscopic damage accumulation. The predicted result showed a good agreement with the experimental data while considering not only the degradation in its fiber reinforcement but also the degradation in its fiber/matrix interface.

Keywords: GFRP, Stress corrosion cracking, Global load sharing, Stress prediction

Introduction

Glass-fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) has superior corrosive resistance compared to metal materials and has various applications such as wind turbine, industrial facility, mirror, marine structural materials, and the like. In fact, GFRP operating in such services are based on damage tolerance design with excessive safety factor against the stress corrosion cracking (SCC): interaction between mechanical factors and environmental agents. Some failure accidents of GFRP after long-term operation under corrosive environments are reported. It is an urgent task to clarify the failure mechanism of SCC in GFRP to assure its long-term reliability and to guarantee its wide spreading application fields.

Majority of the previous works on the SCC in GFRP focused on the macroscopic degradation such as crack propagation and strength degradation in GFRP laminates [1 and 2]. It is obvious that such macroscopic properties of GFRP are dependent to the degradation in its constituents. Therefore, evaluation of the microscopic-damage accumulation inside GFRP constituents is essential in order to investigate the mechanism of SCC in GFRP and to assure its long-term reliability under corrosive environment. Microscopic-damages within GFRP are breakage of fiber reinforcement, micro-crack of resin matrix and debonding of fiber/matrix interface. Besides, Kawada *et al.* established that the embedded glass fiber had almost equal degradation behavior in deionized water and vitriolic environment from that the degradation strongly depends on the diffusion coefficient of water molecule [3].

Present paper deals with the degradation in both fiber reinforcement and fiber/matrix interface caused by long-term SCC and predicts the residual strength of unidirectional

GFRP after long-term SCC. In addition, the SCC tests in present research were held under deionized water at 80°C to enhance the SCC degradation. Fragmentation test of SFC specimen after water immersion was conducted to evaluate the residual fiber strength and interfacial strength individually. Subsequently, tensile test of unidirectional GFRP was conducted to measure its residual strength after water immersion. By substituting the strength degradation in fiber strength and interfacial strength obtained from fragmentation test into global load sharing (GLS), the residual strength of unidirectional GFRP was predicted. The predicted result showed good agreement with the experimental data while considering the degradation in the fiber/matrix interface.

Experimental

Specimens

Dumbbell-shaped single fiber composite (SFC) specimen and bar-shaped unidirectional GFRP used in the present research were both fabricated by press molding. The constituents and the specimen geometries of both specimen used in the present research are described in table 1 and figure 1 individually.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of fiber and matrix

	ECR-Glass	Vinylester
Young's modulus E (GPa)	72.5	3.00
Diameter d (μm)	23.5	-

(a) Single fiber composite

(b) Unidirectional GFRP

Figure 1 Geometry of GFRP specimens.

The curing condition was determined from the DSC test of neat vinylester resin. The curing condition for the vinylester resin was 3 hours at 25°C and post curing was 2 hours at 120°C. Additionally, the pretension was applied to the embedded glass fiber for SFC specimen to compensate for the curing shrinkage of the resin matrix. Furthermore, the waterproof sheathing was applied to both specimens to prevent the direct water penetration from the exposed fiber matrix interface at specimen edge. Present research assumes that the Young's modulus of both ECR-Glass E^f and vinylester resin E^m don't degrade after water immersion (superscript "f" is for the fiber reinforcement, "m" is for the resin matrix, "i" is for the fiber/matrix interface, "SFC" is for SFC specimen by the whole, "comp" is for unidirectional GFRP). The fiber volume content V_f of unidirectional GFRP was determined as 30 %.

Water Absorption Test

The degradation in the fiber reinforcement and the fiber/matrix interface occurs when the water reaches the fiber reinforcement embedded in the resin matrix. Besides, resin matrix expands with water absorption. In order to evaluate its water properties, water absorption test of bar-shaped specimen (140mm×20mm×t2mm) made of neat vinylester resin was conducted. The bar-shaped specimen was immersed in deionized water at 80°C, and its weight gain ΔW and swelling strain ε_{swell}^m were measured. The swelling strain ε_{swell}^m of water absorption test is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Swelling strain of vinylester resin matrix.

The water uptake results in neat vinylester resin show that the saturation is reached by the resin with the immersion time of 70 hours and the swelling strain was determined as $\varepsilon_{swell}^m = 0.20\%$.

Fragmentation Test

To evaluate the degradation in the constituents of GFRP, fragmentation test using the dumbbell shaped SFC specimen was conducted after water immersion. Loading was introduced by means of a 2 kN capacity compact testing machine and the test speed was

0.1 mm/min for the fragmentation test. The number of fiber break points n , applied strain ε^f and interfacial debonding length L_d were measured during the tensile test of SFC specimen. In order to measure the interfacial debonding length L_d , fiber break point was observed through the polarizing plate and the point with the maximum brightness was determined as interfacial debonding tip using image processing. The picture of interfacial debonding in the vicinity of fiber break point is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3 Photograph of interfacial debonding in the vicinity of fiber break point through polarizing plate.

Tensile Test of Unidirectional GFRP

To evaluate the degradation in the strength of the unidirectional GFRP, tensile test after water immersion was conducted. Loading was introduced by means of a 10 kN capacity testing machine and the test speed was 0.1 mm/min for the tensile test of unidirectional GFRP. Besides, no swelling strain ε_{swell}^m was measured after water immersion.

Result and Discussion

Degradation in Fiber Strength

The fiber volume content for SFC specimen is minute ($V_f \approx 0.01\%$) so that the embedded glass fiber expands together with its surrounding resin matrix. Therefore the strain applied to the embedded fiber ε^f is shown as follows;

$$\varepsilon^f = \varepsilon_{app}^{SFC} + \varepsilon_{swell}^m \quad (1)$$

Where ε_{app}^{SFC} is the strain applied to the SFC specimen by the testing machine. The residual strength distribution of embedded glass fiber measured by the fragmentation test is shown in figure 4. Such strength distribution would be evaluated by means of Weibull distribution using the following equation [4].

$$\ln n = \frac{L}{L_0} \left(\frac{E^f \varepsilon^f}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \quad (2)$$

Figure 4 Residual strength distribution of embedded glass fiber after immersion measured by fragmentation test.

Where n is the number of fiber break point, L is the gauge length ($=25$ mm), L_0 is the reference length ($=25$ mm), σ_0 is the scale parameter, m is the shape parameter. By considering the effect of interfacial debonding length to the gage length, the corrected number of fiber break point n' and corrected effective length L' would be as follows [5];

$$\frac{L_0}{n'+1} = \frac{L'}{n+1} \quad (3)$$

Thus, we obtain the relationship between corrected number of fiber break points and the Weibull distribution as following equation.

$$\ln n' = \frac{L'}{L_0} \left(\frac{\sigma^f}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \quad (4)$$

Weibull parameters σ_0 and m used in the evaluation of the fiber strength distribution are shown in table 2.

Table 2 Weibull parameters measured by the fragmentation test

Immersion time t (hour)	0	25	100	300	600	1000
m	9.8	7.8	5.4	5.4	5.3	5.3
σ_0	1500	1200	740	730	700	660

It is obvious from the scale parameter σ_0 that the residual strength of embedded glass fiber degrades drastically in the early stage of water immersion and saturates toward certain strength with long-term immersion. Additionally, the dispersion of strength distribution seems to increase with immersion time. This is because that the mechanism of fiber strength is dependent to the flaw on the fiber surface with dispersed size, and by applying the SCC to the embedded fiber leads to the growth of its surface flaw. Besides, its growth rate depends on its flaw size and therefore the SCC expands the dispersion in the flaw size, resulting in the increase in shape parameter m .

Degradation in Interfacial Strength

Elastic analysis of the axial fiber stress σ^f and the interfacial shear stress τ^i in the vicinity of the fiber break point considering the swelling stresses of the resin matrix (axial stress $\sigma_{z,\text{swell}}^m$ and radial stress $\sigma_{r,\text{swell}}^m$) are shown in figure 5 and following equations [6 and 7].

Figure 5 Elastic analysis of stress distribution considering interfacial debonding.

(i) $0 \leq z \leq L_d$

$$\tau^i(z) = (H_{1i} - \mu\sigma_{r,\text{swell}}^m) \exp(-\alpha z) \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma^f(z) = \frac{H_{1i}}{H_{2i}} (1 - \exp(-\alpha z)) \quad (6)$$

(ii) $L_d < z$

$$\tau^i(z) = \tau_{\max}^i \exp \beta(L_d - z) \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma^f(z) = \sigma_0^f + \sigma_{z,\text{swell}}^m - \frac{4\tau_{\max}^i}{\beta d^f} \exp \beta(L_d - z) \quad (8)$$

Where μ is the coefficient of friction, σ_0^f is the axial stress of remote unbroken fiber, H_{1i} is the function of σ_0^f , $\sigma_{r,swell}^f$ is the stress from the swelling resin matrix (122 MPa), α , β , and H_{2i} are constants. H_{1i} and H_{2i} are shown in following equations.

$$H'_{1i} = \frac{\mu \nu^m E^m (\sigma_0^f + \sigma_{z,swell}^m)}{(1 - \nu^f) E^m + (1 + \nu^m) E^f} \quad (9)$$

$$H_{2i} = \frac{\mu \nu^f E^m E^f}{(1 - \nu^f) E^m + (1 + \nu^m) E^f} \quad (10)$$

Where ν^f and ν^m are the Poisson ration of glass fiber and vinylester resin. Present research evaluated the interfacial strength as the interfacial shear strength τ_{max}^i at the debonding tip L_d . The interfacial shear strength τ_{max}^i is shown in following equation.

$$\tau_{max}^i = \frac{\beta d^f}{4} \left[\sigma_0^f + \sigma_{z,swell}^m - \frac{H_{1i}}{H_{2i}} (1 - \exp(-\alpha L_d)) \right] \quad (11)$$

The interfacial shear strength τ_{max}^i versus the immersion time is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6 Interfacial shear strength after hot immersion obtained from fragmentation test.

It is obvious that the interfacial shear strength degrades in the early stage of water immersion and seems to saturate toward certain strength with long-term immersion (60% of its initial strength). Possible explanations for this behavior are as follows; (i) the counterpoise in the hydrolysis of silane coupling agent, (ii) the complete elution of silane coupling agent.

Residual Strength of Unidirectional GFRP

Tensile test of unidirectional GFRP was conducted in air to determine the residual strength after water immersion. The residual strength of unidirectional GFRP obtained from tensile test is shown in figure 7.

Figure 7 Residual strength of unidirectional GFRP after water immersion.

The residual strength and the rupture strain of unidirectional GFRP degrades in the early stage of water immersion and seems to saturate toward certain strength with long-term immersion; it is natural to have such behavior because its constituents had the similar strength degradation behavior (σ_0 and τ_{max}^i). Although the strength of fiber reinforcement σ_0 decreased to 43% of its initial value, the strength of unidirectional GFRP dropped to 60% of its initial strength. This is because the fiber strength wasn't the only factor to determine the unidirectional strength and the strength of unidirectional FRP varies with its interfacial strength [8].

The strength was predicted using the following method. The prediction was based on the global load sharing (GLS) model [9]. The interfacial strength decreases with the water immersion and therefore relaxation of the strength concentration in the intact unbroken fiber around the broken fiber occurs leading to the assumption of GLS model. The stress recovery length in the vicinity of fiber break point considering the interfacial debonding length is shown in following equation.

$$L'_r = L_r + L_d \quad (12)$$

At interfacial debonding tip ($z=L_d$) equation (6) and (8) satisfies the continuity condition, and therefore the debonding length would be as follows;

$$L_d = -\frac{1}{\alpha} \ln \left[1 - \frac{H_2}{H_{1i}} \left(\sigma_0^f + \sigma_{z,swell}^m - \frac{4\tau_{max}}{\beta d^f} \right) \right] \quad (13)$$

The average stress applied to the fiber in unidirectional GFRP would be expressed as the following equation using the Weibull distribution.

$$\sigma_{res}^{comp} = \sigma_0^f \cdot [1 - P(\sigma_0^f)] + \sigma_b^f \left(\frac{L_r'}{4} \right) \cdot P(\sigma_0^f) \quad (14)$$

Where $\sigma_b^f \left(\frac{L_r'}{4} \right)$ is the average stress in broken fiber. By substituting the result from the fragmentation test into equation (14) the predicted residual strength would be calculated as figure 8. The result of strength prediction considering the degradation in fiber reinforcement is drawn in dotted line and result considering both the fiber/matrix interface is drawn in solid line.

Figure 8 Predicted residual strength of unidirectional GFRP after water immersion.

The predicted result also decreased in the early stage of immersion and saturated toward certain strength, because the strength of unidirectional GFRP is strongly dependent to the strength of fiber reinforcement. In addition, it is obvious that the predicted strength and the experimental plot showed good agreement after long-term immersion while considering the degradation in fiber/matrix interface. This was because the interfacial strength decreased with the SCC in fiber/matrix interface, therefore relaxation of the stress concentration due to the broken fiber occurred, and led to the condition similar to the assumption of GLS model.

Conclusion

Water immersion of the GFRP results in the degradation in its constituents and therefore lead to the decrease of its mechanical properties. Present paper conducted the fragmentation test and the tensile test of E-glass/vinylester composite after water

immersion at 80°C. Based on the result of this study, the following conclusions were obtained.

- (i) Fragmentation test of SFC specimen after water immersion at 80°C was conducted to evaluate the strength of embedded glass fiber reinforcement and the fiber/matrix interface. The strength of both the fiber reinforcement and the fiber/matrix interface decreased drastically in the early stage of immersion and saturated toward certain strength.
- (ii) Tensile test of unidirectional GFRP was conducted to evaluate the residual strength after water immersion at 80°C. The residual strength and the rupture strain of unidirectional GFRP decreased drastically in the early stage of water immersion and saturated toward certain strength.
- (iii) The residual strength of unidirectional GFRP was predicted using global load sharing (GLS) model considering the degradation in its constituents. By considering both the degradation in the fiber reinforcement and the fiber/matrix interface, The residual strength was predicted in good agreement with the experimental data.

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